

STRUCTURE, COMPONENTS AND FUNCTIONS OF LINGUOCULTURAL COMPETENCE**Murodilla Marufovich Yakubbaev***Namangan Institute of Foreign Languages,
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This scientific article is decided to further research a detailed analysis of the content, structure and functions of linguocultural competence. Linguocultural competence is interpreted as the ability to carry out intercultural communication in the process of learning a foreign language. The work describes the interdependence and complementarity of language, cultural and communicative competences, as well as the communicative, cognitive, moral and educational functions of this competence. It is based on the importance of linguocultural competence in the modern education system and its role in ensuring the success of a person in intercultural communication.

Keywords: linguocultural competence, structure, main components and functions, language teaching methodology.

Introduction. In the 21st century, globalization and integration processes have dramatically increased the importance of intercultural communication between representatives of different nationalities and cultures. As a result of these processes, linguocultural competence, that is, the ability to take cultural aspects into account when communicating in a foreign language, has become an important component of the modern education system. Kunanbayeva S. (2013) Today, the importance of linguocultural competence is increasing not only in the process of learning foreign languages, but also in professional activity, scientific research and various aspects of everyday life. Saniyazova S. (2021)

The scope of scientific research and practical developments aimed at understanding the nature of linguocultural competence and determining the ways of its formation is expanding. Therefore, it is important to study the structure, components and functions of this competence. This is necessary not only for the development of the language teaching methodology, but also for ensuring the success of a person in intercultural communication.

In order to gain a deeper understanding of the content of linguocultural competence and its main components, this article analyzes its main aspects in detail. Communicative, cognitive, moral and educational functions of linguocultural competence are also considered. This analysis reveals not only the theoretical importance of linguocultural competence, but also its role in practical application.

Materials and Methods.

The need for the development of linguocultural competence. As a result of the processes of globalization, international integration and migration, contacts between representatives of different nationalities and cultures have increased. These processes force people to get to know different cultures, learn their languages, and communicate with intercultural differences in mind. (Brooks, N. (1968)). Therefore, linguocultural competence should include not only linguistic knowledge, but also cultural knowledge. Through this competence, individuals acquire the skills to communicate appropriately and effectively in different cultural contexts.

Research and practical development. Given the importance of linguocultural competence, many scientific studies and practical developments are being conducted in this area. Researches in the fields of linguistics, pedagogy, sociology and psychology are aimed at studying various aspects of linguocultural competence. These studies help to identify strategies for the development of intercultural communication in the process of learning a foreign language. At the same time, practical developments are aimed at developing various methods and tools for the formation and development of linguocultural competence.

The importance of the linguocultural competence. Linguistic-cultural competence is an important conceptual concept in the theory and practice of modern language education. This competence includes the interrelationship of language and culture, skills and abilities necessary for intercultural communication. This competence covers not only linguistic knowledge, but also cultural concepts and helps to understand the complex connections between them.

The connection of language and culture is inseparable. Understanding the relationship between language and culture is one of the central aspects of linguocultural competence. Language is a means of expression of culture, and culture shapes the content and functions of language. Cultural values, customs, social norms and worldviews are expressed through language. Thus, in the process of learning a language, there is a need to learn various aspects of culture. Understanding this interdependence is important for successful foreign language learning and intercultural communication.

Cross-cultural differences. The ability to understand and adapt to intercultural differences is an important component of linguocultural competence. Each culture has its own social, cultural and communicative norms and value system. Understanding these differences and treating them with respect is necessary for successful intercultural communication. The ability to successfully perform communicative tasks, taking into account intercultural differences, determines the level of linguocultural competence of a person.

Linguocultural integration. Linguocultural competence combines linguocultural knowledge. Linguistic knowledge includes phonetic, lexical, grammatical and

stylistic skills. Cultural knowledge covers customs, traditions, values, social norms and other aspects of culture. By combining these two types of knowledge, an individual will be able to succeed in intercultural communication. Combining linguocultural knowledge increases the ability of a person to perform communicative tasks in a foreign language, taking into account the cultural context.

The connection between language and culture, the reflection of a certain national culture in the language, and therefore the problem of learning this language by integrating it with the national culture has only been studied in recent years. It is mentioned in the researches of many scientists that the elements of the linguocultural component of foreign language teaching consist of the characteristics of the national mentality in spiritual and material values. Linguistics knowledge includes non-equivalent and background lexis and the ways of its expression in the native language, cultural (i.e., cultural) signs of authentic texts, rules of speech behavior of language speakers. (M. Mirkosimova 2023)

Linguocultural competence ensures that a person succeeds in the process of learning a foreign language and in intercultural communication. This competence helps to increase a person's cultural level, expand his worldview, and develop respect and tolerance for other cultures. Linguocultural competence also develops the skills necessary for effective communication in international business, diplomacy, education and other fields.

Thus, linguocultural competence not only increases the effectiveness of the language learning process, but also greatly contributes to the overall cultural and moral development of a person. This competence is essential to ensure an individual's success in intercultural communication and effective communication in the global world.

The structure of linguocultural competence.

The structure of linguocultural competence consists of several main components, which are interrelated and complement each other. These components include important elements such as language, culture and communication, which help to build the knowledge and skills necessary for effective intercultural communication. (Rizayeva D., 2019) The structure of linguocultural competence consists of three main components: language competence, cultural competence and communicative competence.

Language competence. Language competence is one of the main components of linguocultural competence. This component includes phonetic, lexical, grammatical and stylistic aspects of the language. (Maslova, V. (2001) Language competence includes all linguistic knowledge necessary for clear and understandable communication in a foreign language. This knowledge includes the following elements:

- phonetic knowledge: knowing the sound system and phonetic features of the language, the ability to pronounce correctly.
- lexical knowledge: vocabulary, meaning of words, their contextual use and understanding of synonymous, antonymic relationships.

- grammatic knowledge: knowledge related to the grammatical rules of the language, sentence structure, syntax and morphology.

- stylistic knowledge: correct use of stylistic aspects of the language in different communicative situations, knowledge of language registers and stylistic nuances.

Language competence includes not only linguistic knowledge, but also the ability to use it correctly in the process of communication. This competence forms the linguistic foundations necessary for effective communication in a foreign language.

Cultural competence. Cultural competence is an important component of linguocultural competence and includes the ability to understand and respect other cultures. This component includes the following elements:

- cultural knowledge: knowledge of foreign cultures, including customs, traditions, values and social norms.

- cross-cultural awareness: the ability to understand and adapt to cross-cultural differences. these differences can be manifested in language, non-verbal communication, cultural behavior and social norms.

- respect for culture: respect other cultures, treat different cultural phenomena with tolerance and understanding. The cultural component of the environment is no less important than its linguistic component (Mukhamadiarova Albina; Merkish Nataliya; Kulkova Mariya, 2018).

Cultural competence is necessary for a person to successfully participate in intercultural communication. Through this competence, the individual will be able to behave appropriately in different cultural contexts and avoid intercultural conflicts.

Communicative competence. Communicative competence is one of the main components of linguocultural competence, and it is the ability to communicate effectively using language and cultural knowledge. This component includes the following elements:

- written and verbal communication skills: knowing the strategies and techniques needed to carry out written and verbal communication in a foreign language.

- pragmatic skills: pragmatic skills necessary for successful participation in intercultural communication, including choosing appropriate and correct behaviors in different communicative situations.

- interactive strategies: using interactive strategies to establish effective relationships with representatives of different cultures in the communication process.

Communicative competence develops a person's ability to communicate effectively and successfully in a foreign language. Through this competence, the individual will be able to perform communicative tasks correctly and effectively in different cultural contexts.

Functions of linguocultural competence. Linguocultural competence performs several main functions, among which communicative, cognitive, moral and educational functions are distinguished. These functions reveal many aspects of linguocultural competence and emphasize its importance in interpersonal communication. (Kaplan, 1966; Kaplan, 1972).

Communicative function. Communicative function is one of the main functions of linguocultural competence. This function includes all the skills and knowledge necessary for effective communication in a foreign language. Communicative function allows successful communication taking into account intercultural differences. This feature includes:

- oral and written communication: ability to communicate effectively, both verbally and in writing, in different cultural contexts.

- communication strategies: applying the strategies and techniques needed to establish and maintain effective relationships in intercultural communication.

- adaptation to cultural context: developing flexibility and communicative adaptability in different cultural contexts.

Cognitive function. Cognitive function makes it possible to acquire and expand intercultural knowledge through linguocultural competence. This function helps to study and understand the foreign culture in depth, which increases the general cultural level of the individual (Palmer, 1996). This feature includes:

- knowledge acquisition: acquisition of broad knowledge about foreign culture, including history, literature, art and other cultural aspects.

- awareness of cultural differences: understanding the characteristics of different cultures and communicating with them in mind.

- analytical skills: to develop the ability to analyze cross-cultural situations and evaluate them correctly.

Educational function. The educational function implies the development of a person's ability to behave correctly in intercultural communication through linguocultural competence. This function contributes to the general cultural and moral development of a person. This feature includes:

- cultural literacy: to increase the cultural literacy of the individual and to develop the ability to behave appropriately in different cultural contexts.

- ethical education: formation of moral education and behavior skills in intercultural communication.

- personal development: contributing to the overall development of the individual through intercultural communication, broadening his worldview and achieving cultural diversification.

These functions of linguocultural competence ensure a person's successful participation in intercultural communication and greatly contribute to his general cultural and moral development. This competence enables an individual to behave appropriately in different cultural contexts, to communicate effectively and to establish successful relationships taking into account cultural differences.

Conclusion and recommendations. Linguocultural competence occupies an important place in the modern education system. A detailed understanding of the structure, components and functions of this competence is necessary for effective intercultural communication. The interdependence and complementarity of language, cultural and communicative competences contribute to the full implementation of linguocultural competence. At the same time, the communicative,

cognitive, moral and educational functions of this competence ensure the success of a person in intercultural communication.

The structure of linguocultural competence consists of linguistic, cultural and communicative components. Each component has its own importance and functions. Language competence develops the phonetic, lexical, grammatical and stylistic knowledge of a person, while cultural competence forms the ability to understand and respect other cultures. Communicative competence develops the ability to effectively use language and cultural knowledge in intercultural communication. Together, these components fully form the linguocultural competence of a person.

Communicative, cognitive, moral and educational functions of linguocultural competence ensure the success of a person in intercultural communication. Communicative function ensures the implementation of communication through the effective use of language and cultural knowledge, while cognitive function allows the acquisition and expansion of intercultural knowledge. The ethical function develops the ability to maintain and respect ethical standards in intercultural communication. Educational function forms a person's ability to behave correctly in intercultural communication and contributes to general cultural and moral development. Theoretical and practical aspects of linguocultural competence are important for its study and development. This competence includes theoretically the basic principles of intercultural communication and practically the skills to communicate successfully with different cultures. The development of linguocultural competence helps to prepare pupils and students as effective citizens in the global world.

Summary. In short, linguocultural competence plays an important role in the modern education system and plays a decisive role in ensuring the success of a person in intercultural communication. The interdependence and complementarity of language, cultural and communicative components contribute to the full realization of linguocultural competence. Communicative, cognitive, moral and educational functions ensure a person's successful participation in intercultural communication. Therefore, the development of linguocultural competence not only increases the efficiency of the language learning process, but also contributes greatly to the overall cultural and moral development of a person.

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